

Comparative Study of MgO, SiO₂, and Al₂O₃ Insulation Materials in Mineral-Insulated Cables Under Thermal, Electrical, Mechanical, and Radiation Stress

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Abstract— The long-term performance of power and instrumentation cables in nuclear, aerospace, and defense environments depends strongly on insulation stability under thermal, electrical, mechanical, and radiation stresses.

Organic, and even some cross-linked, polymer insulations degrade rapidly in such conditions, accelerating the use of ceramic and mineral-based alternatives. This paper addresses magnesium oxide (MgO), silicon dioxide (SiO₂), and aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) as cable insulation materials.

Electrical, thermal, mechanical, and radiation resistance properties are reviewed based on available published data. Recent tests of nuclear-instrument cables under γ radiation ($\sim 10^5$ R/h) and elevated temperature (~ 450 °C)

demonstrated that SiO₂ insulation achieved insulation resistances nearly two decades higher than MgO or Al₂O₃ when impurities and backfill gases were tightly controlled. Additionally, high-energy physics applications show MgO-insulated MI cables can withstand up to $\sim 10^9$ Gy and quartz-based SiO₂ up to $\sim 10^{10}$ Gy. Results indicate MgO provides excellent thermal stability and radiation tolerance but is moisture-sensitive, SiO₂ can outperform under specific high-radiation conditions, and Al₂O₃ achieves stability across all categories, making it the most versatile for nuclear and aerospace power applications.

Keywords—MgO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Mineral Insulated Cables, MI Cable, Fire Protection, Thermal Resistance, Radiation Resistance

I. INTRODUCTION

Power cable insulation must have very high reliability in demanding environments such as nuclear reactors, aerospace craft, particle accelerators, and defensive systems. In these applications, insulators are exposed to elevated temperatures, strong electrical fields, mechanical stresses, and ionizing radiation. Organic and some cross-linked polymer-based insulations, that are widely used in conventional power and communication cables, degrade under such conditions, exhibiting embrittlement, carbonization, and dielectric breakdown [1].

Inorganic ceramics and minerals provide a more durable alternative. Their built-in resistance to heat, radiation, and combustion has driven interest in their deployment for mineral-insulated (MI) cables and high-voltage systems [2]. Among the top contenders, MgO, SiO₂, and Al₂O₃ are particularly worth review. MgO is established in MI cables and thermocouples, SiO₂ is used in MI cables and is central to high-voltage and optical systems, and Al₂O₃ is widely applied in nuclear and aerospace components.

Traditionally, SiO₂ has been considered more vulnerable to radiation-induced degradation than MgO or Al₂O₃ [5], [7]. However, Cannon et al. [13] showed that SiO₂ insulation can achieve superior insulation resistance under simultaneous γ irradiation and elevated temperature. More recently, Hannah

[14] reviewed MI cable performance in particle accelerators, showing MgO insulation tolerates up to $\sim 10^9$ Gy and quartz-based SiO₂ can reach $\sim 10^{10}$ Gy radiation resistance, confirming their excellent use case for extreme environments. Of note, in reactor applications, Neutron fluence can produce displacement damage, swelling and dielectric abnormal behaviours. Materials can be altered at the atomic level.

II. REVIEW OF AVAILABLE RESEARCH

A. Mineral-Insulated Cables

MI cables consist of metallic (copper and nickel alloy) conductors encased in a sheath (copper, aluminum, stainless steel or Inconel's) and compacted with powdered inorganic insulation, typically MgO. These cables are naturally fire-resistant, non-flammable, and capable of continuous operation at 250 °C or higher depending on the conductor, insulation and cable sheath materials, with short-term survivability above 1000 °C or higher [2], [3].

B. Magnesium Oxide (MgO)

MgO has a high melting point (2852 °C) and thermal conductivity in the range of 45–60 W/m·K [3]. It maintains dielectric stability up to 250 °C, though resistivity decreases with increasing temperature. Its hygroscopic nature is a major limitation: moisture ingress degrades insulation resistance and requires sealing strategies [4]. Radiation induces oxygen vacancies and F-centers, but MgO retains dielectric and structural integrity, making it reliable for nuclear instrumentation [5]. Hannah [14] adds that MgO-based MI cables endure up to $\sim 10^9$ Gy with acceptable performance, confirming its place as a leading insulator in accelerators and reactors.

C. Silicon Dioxide (SiO₂)

SiO₂ offers dielectric strengths of 4–9 MV/cm and resistivities of 10^{15} – 10^{17} Ω ·cm at DC [6]. Amorphous SiO₂ has low thermal conductivity (~ 1.4 W/m·K) and is vulnerable to ionizing radiation, which introduces trapped charge, leakage currents, and optical darkening [7]. Crystalline quartz demonstrates improved stability but is still less radiation-resistant than MgO or Al₂O₃ in many conditions [8]. Cannon et al. [13] reported that SiO₂-insulated nuclear-instrument cables achieved insulation resistance $> 10^{10}$ Ω ·ft at 450 °C and γ dose rates of 10^5 R/h, nearly two decades higher than MgO or Al₂O₃. Hannah [14] further shows quartz-based SiO₂ can survive up to $\sim 10^{10}$ Gy, making it the most radiation-hard material in certain avionics and accelerator applications.

D. Aluminum Oxide (Al₂O₃)

Al₂O₃ combines strong dielectric strength (14–17 kV/mm) with moderate thermal conductivity (20–30 W/m·K) and excellent mechanical strength (300–600 MPa

flexural, 2000–4000 MPa compressive) [9], [10]. It remains stable at temperatures up to 1700 °C. Under neutron and gamma flux, alumina exhibits excellent resistance to degradation, with partial defect recovery achievable through annealing [11], [12].

III. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

TABLE I — COMPARATIVE PROPERTIES OF MgO, SiO₂ AND AL₂O₃

Property	MgO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃
Dielectric Strength	6–10 kV/mm [3], [4]	4–9 MV/cm [6]	14–17 kV/mm [9]
Resistivity	~10 ¹² Ω·cm [4]	10 ¹⁵ –10 ¹⁷ Ω·cm [6]	10 ¹⁴ –10 ¹⁵ Ω·cm [9]
Thermal Conductivity	45–60 W/m·K [3]	1.4 W/m·K (amorphous) [7]	20–30 W/m·K [9]
Max Operating Temp	250 °C cont., >1000 °C short-term [4]	~1000 °C (quartz) [7]	~1700 °C [10]
Mechanical Strength	Brittle, hygroscopic [4]	Brittle, fracture-prone [7]	300–600 MPa, 2000–4000 MPa comp. [10]
Radiation Resistance	Good; up to ~10 ⁹ Gy [14]	Poor in bulk films; but >10 ¹⁰ Ω·ft IR at 450 °C + γ [13], quartz up to 10 ¹⁰ Gy [14]	Excellent; stable, with annealing recovery [11]
Applications	MI cables, nuclear thermocouples, accelerators [2], [14]	Microelectronics, reactors, avionics, nuclear instrumentation [6], [13], [14]	Nuclear HV insulators [9]

IV. DISCUSSION

The comparison highlights significant trade-offs. MgO provides high thermal conductivity, strong dielectric performance, and radiation resistance up to ~10⁹ Gy, making it ideal for MI cables in reactors and accelerators [14]. SiO₂ excels in dielectric strength and resistivity, and Cannon et al. [13] show it can outperform MgO and Al₂O₃ in insulation resistance at high γ dose and temperature, while Hannah [14] confirms quartz-based SiO₂ can tolerate up to 10¹⁰ Gy. However, SiO₂ remains mechanically fragile and sensitive in amorphous form. Al₂O₃ demonstrates the most balanced performance across electrical, thermal, and radiation categories, with proven use in nuclear and aerospace power systems.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper reviewed MgO, SiO₂, and Al₂O₃ insulation materials for cables in extreme environments. MgO remains the cornerstone of MI cable design, capable of withstanding up to 10⁹ Gy in accelerators and reactors [14]. SiO₂, once considered radiation-vulnerable, has shown superior insulation resistance in controlled nuclear-instrumentation tests [13] and quartz-based SiO₂ can tolerate up to 10¹⁰ Gy [14], extending its use in avionics and accelerator systems. Al₂O₃ offers robust, well-rounded performance across all categories, making it the most versatile option for long-life power applications in nuclear and aerospace contexts. Future work should explore hybrid insulations and optimized MI cable geometries (hollow vs. solid core) to exploit the complementary strengths of these ceramics.

VI. REFERENCES

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